

THE IMPORTANCE OF KVEST TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article highlights the pedagogical possibilities of KVEST technologies in developing critical thinking skills in preschool children. During the study, the impact of interactive activities based on quests on children's independent thinking, problem-solving skills, communication culture, and creative activity was analyzed. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of quest technologies in the preschool education process.

Keywords: critical thinking, KVEST technology, preschool education, interactive method, pedagogical technology, creative thinking, innovative education.

In the modern education system, developing children's intellectual potential and teaching them to think independently and critically is considered one of the important pedagogical tasks. Especially preschool age is the most important stage in which a child's thinking, worldview, and cognitive activity are formed. Therefore, during this period, it is important to develop children's logical thinking, problem-solving skills, and independent decision-making.

Traditional teaching methods often limit children's activity. As a result, the child is formed as a subject who receives ready-made knowledge. Modern pedagogical technologies present the child as an active participant. One such innovative technology is the KVEST technology. This technology encourages children to search, solve problem situations, and draw independent conclusions.

KVEST technology is based on a combination of play, adventure, and tasks, and is suitable for the psychology of preschool children. This is because children of this age acquire knowledge quickly and effectively through play activities. In this regard, quest classes serve as an effective tool for developing critical thinking in children.

Today, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the education system is gaining significant importance. Particularly in the preschool education system, one of the urgent tasks is the development of children's independent thinking and teaching them to make correct decisions in problematic situations. Preschool is a period when a child's thinking, worldview, and cognitive processes are actively formed, and it is at this stage that the development of critical thinking skills in children determines the effectiveness of the subsequent educational process. From this perspective, the use of KVEST technologies is emerging as an effective tool for developing children's thinking activities.

Critical thinking is the process of analyzing data, comparing it, drawing conclusions, and finding independent solutions to problems. In preschool children, this skill is formed through simple questions and answers, logical games, observations, and interactive tasks. The child tries to understand the surrounding events, asking questions such as "Why?," "How?," "Why?." This indicates that his thinking process is actively developing. The educator's task is to support this interest in the child and direct it correctly.

Among modern pedagogical technologies, the KVEST technology holds a special place. The word "quest" translated from English means "search," "adventure." This technology is based on achieving a goal through the sequential execution of tasks and encourages children to take active action. During quest sessions, children encounter various problem situations, complete tasks, conduct research, and reach final conclusions. This process develops their independent and critical thinking.

When using KVEST technologies in preschool education, the age characteristics and interests of children must be taken into account. Quest activities are usually organized based on fairy-tale characters, magical events, or adventure plots. For example, topics such as "Finding a Lost Treasure," "Looking for the Magic Key," or "Helping a Hero" will be of great interest to children. During the lesson, children are given logical and creative tasks. They perform tasks such as finding a superfluous object, determining cause and effect, solving riddles, or composing a story based on a drawing. Such tasks not only develop children's thinking but also develop their ability to observe and analyze.

One of the important aspects of KVEST technology is the organization of collective activities. Children learn to solve problems together by working in small groups. This develops a culture of communication, cooperation, and the ability to freely express one's thoughts. During group work, children learn to listen to others' opinions, jointly analyze the problem, and reach a common decision. As a result, they not only gain knowledge but also develop their social competencies.

Another advantage of quest activities is that they increase children's interest in the lesson. Assignments enriched with game elements encourage children to participate actively. Even children who participate slowly in normal activities become active during the quest. Because play is the most natural type of activity for children. Education organized through play will be effective and interesting.

Research indicates that the use of KVEST technologies develops children's skills in independent thinking, problem-solving, rapid decision-making, and a creative approach. At the same time, children's self-confidence increases, and speech activity and communicative competencies are strengthened. Most importantly, the child becomes not a recipient of ready-made knowledge, but an active subject seeking and analyzing knowledge.

In conclusion, the use of KVEST technologies in the development of critical thinking in preschool children is one of the important

directions of modern pedagogy. This technology teaches children to think independently, analyze problems, conduct research, and draw correct conclusions. Therefore, the widespread use of KVEST technologies in preschool educational organizations is of great importance for the intellectual and creative development of children.

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